

New Baths for the Deposition of Manganese and Cobalt Oxides

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New methods have been adopted for the anodic deposition of the different manganese and cobalt oxides. The deposition of the different oxides is usually carried out from their metal salt solutions in presence of a complexing agent or a reducing agent. The oxides deposited are as follows: Mn_2O_3 from manganous sulphate in presence of boric acid and formaldehyde at $pH=5.5$, Mn_2O_4 from manganous sulphate in presence of formic acid at $pH=5.0$, MnO from manganous sulphate-ammonium chloride solution in presence of telluric acid, Co_2O_3 from cobalt chloride in presence of telluric acid and sodium fluoride, Co_3O_4 from cobaltite in presence of formaldehyde and potassium chloride and finally CoO from cobalt chloride in presence of alcohol. The results of chemical analysis revealed that the purity of the oxides is 99.99% and their molecular formulae are $MnO_{1.2}$, $MnO_{1.33}$, MnO , $CoO_{1.5}$, $CoO_{1.33}$ and CoO respectively.

ANODIC formation of Mn^{+2} and Mn^{+3} was observed by Agladze and Kharabadze¹ during the polarization of manganese in sulphuric acid solutions of different concentration. Bellone² found that insoluble compounds of a lower state of oxidation than MnO_2 could be obtained by electrolysis in a solution of alkali metal halide. Grube and Feucht³ studied anodic oxidation of a solution of cobaltite and detected the formation of CoO , Co_2O_4 and CoO_2 at low, medium and high potentials respectively. Wernicke⁴ and Goehn and Glaser⁵ obtained cobaltic oxide di-hydrate by electrolysis of a solution of potassium cobalt-tartrate in potash-lye and drying the product in vacuum.

In the present investigation some oxides of manganese and cobalt were prepared by electro-deposition from baths containing the metal salt in presence of a complexing or a reducing agent.

Experimental

Materials and Apparatus

Standard solutions of manganous sulphate and cobaltous chloride were prepared from analar materials dissolved in double distilled water and their concentrations determined as described in Vogel⁶. Other materials used such as ammonium chloride, ammonium sulphate, boric acid, telluric acid, formic acid, formaldehyde, sodium carbonate, sodium fluoride and potassium chloride were prepared by dissolving the appropriate amount of A.R. or recrystallised material in double distilled water. For the electro-deposition of the different oxides an electrolytic cell with two compartments separated by a porous diaphragm was used. Each compartment, is provided with a platinum wire. The

electrolysing current was supplied from a 6-volt storage battery. Current regulation was maintained by a resistance box connected in series. It is to be noted that in all the cases of electro-deposition of the oxides of manganese and cobalt the bath temperature was maintained at 25°.

The Electrodeposition of Manganese and Cobalt Oxides

1— Mn_2O_3

The boric acid-formaldehyde bath: The electrolyte was prepared by mixing 5 ml 0.99 N $MnSO_4$ solution, 25 ml double distilled water, 5 gm NH_4Cl and 0.302 gm boric acid. The solution was heated to dissolve the salts and after cooling 0.1 ml 6 N formaldehyde solution was added. The acid solution was then neutralised with 3.2 ml ammonia solution up to $pH=5.5$. The current density used amounts to 1 m.A./ cm^2 .

2— Mn_2O_4

The formic acid-ammonium sulphate bath: The electrolyte was prepared by mixing 4 ml 0.99 N $MnSO_4$ solution, 25 ml double distilled water, 0.1 ml 6 N formaldehyde solution 10 gm ammonium sulphate. The solution was boiled to dissolve the salt and then neutralised with 4.5 ml ammonium hydroxide to $pH=5.0$. The current density used amounts to 0.3 m.A./ cm^2 .

3— MnO

The formate-pyrogallol bath: The electrolyte was prepared by mixing 5 ml 0.99 N $MnSO_4$ solution, 25 ml distilled water and 5 gm ammonium chloride. The solution was heated to dissolve the salt followed by adding 0.1 ml 6 N formaldehyde and 0.473 gm pyrogallol. The pH of the solution was maintained

at 3 using concentrated sulphuric acid. The current density used amounts to 1 m.A./cm².

4—Co₂O₃

The tellurate-sodium fluoride bath : The electrolyte was prepared by mixing 50 ml 0.15 N CoCl₂ solution, 1 gm telluric acid and 1 gm sodium fluoride. The current density used amounts to 1 m.A./cm².

5—Co₃O₄

The cobaltite-formaldehyde bath : In this case anodic deposition of Co₃O₄ was carried out from an electrolyte prepared by dissolving 13 gm NaOH in 20 ml 0.15 M CoCl₂ followed by adding 0.1 ml 6 N formaldehyde solution so that the final concentration of the alkali is 14.7 M.

To this solution 10 gm potassium chloride were added and the cobaltite solution heated to dissolve the salt. The current density applied amounts to 0.5 m.A./cm².

6—CoO

The sodium carbonate-alcohol bath : The electrolyte was prepared by mixing 50 ml 0.15 N CoCl₂ solution, 2 gm Na₂CO₃, 20 gm NaCl and 20 ml absolute alcohol. The current density applied was 0.5 m.A./cm².

Discussion

Mechanism of Oxide Formation

The formation of the different oxides studied is believed to take place as follows :

1—Mn₂O₃ : During the deposition of Mn₂O₃ oxide, the migration of the complex species, manganese borate [Mn(B₄O₇)₂]⁻¹, towards the anode occurs where it loses its charge and dissociates yielding Mn⁺³ or Mn⁺⁴ ions. These ions react with OH⁻ ions forming Mn₂O₃.

2—Mn₃O₄ : The deposition of Mn₃O₄ oxide takes place by the migration of the [Mn(CO₃H)₃]⁻¹ species to the anode which on discharge and reaction with OH⁻ ions yields Mn₃O₄.

3—MnO : During the deposition of MnO from the formate-pyrogallol bath migration of [Mn(CO₃H)₃]⁻¹ species to the anode takes place. Direct discharge of the complex species takes place furnishing Mn⁺² ions. These ionic species react with OH⁻ ions yielding the oxide.

4—Co₂O₃ : The deposition of Co₂O₃ from the tellurate bath is supposed to take place by the anodic migration of the ionic species [Co(TeO₄)₂]⁻², which loses its charge producing Co⁺² or Co⁺³ ions. These ions react with OH⁻ ions forming the oxide.

5—Co₃O₄ : The deposition of Co₃O₄ from the cobaltite bath takes place by the migration of CoO₂⁻ species towards the anode, which on discharge yields

CoO⁺ or Co⁺³ ions and under the effect of the reducing agent produces Co₃O₄.

6—CoO : The deposition of CoO from the CoCl₂-alcohol takes place by the migration of the cobalt dialcoholate complex [Co(EtO)₂]⁻¹ towards the anode which on discharge yields Co⁺² or Co⁺³ ions and under the effect of the reducing agent produces CoO.

The formation of Mn⁺³, Mn⁺⁴ and Co⁺³ have been proved by Kharabadze and Grube^{5,7} during the anodic oxidation of manganese or cobaltite.

From the literature of manganese complexes, Senet and Sanz⁸ proved the structure of the manganic ditartrate complex as [Mn(C₃H₂O₃)₂]⁻¹. Similarly it is probable that a diborate complex exists. The formation of cobalt tellurate complex has been proved experimentally by heating cobaltous chloride with telluric acid in presence of H₂O₂, where a brown precipitate is formed. Similarly it is known that cobalt and manganese can form dialcoholate complexes.

The Effect of Complexing Agent/Metal Ion Ratio

Increase in the concentration of the complexing agent with Mn₂O₃ causes the deposition of a lower oxide due to the low concentration of the metal ions provided by the dissociation of the metal complex at the anode. On the other hand, increase of the metal ion/complexing agent ratio favours the deposition of a higher oxide.

The Effect of the Concentration of the Reducing Agent

The effect of the concentration of the reducing agents such as formaldehyde, or alcohol was studied during the deposition of Co₂O₃, MnO and CoO. Deposition of a higher oxide takes place in absence or at low concentration of the reducing agent. The role played by these reducing agents is attributed to their reducing properties on the higher oxidation products. The reducing power of formaldehyde increases with rise of pH and its concentration producing an oxide containing a high percentage of the lower oxide.

The Effect of pH

The effect of the pH of the bath on the oxide formed is quite important. Thus it has been observed that the optimum pH in the deposition of the oxides Mn₂O₃, Mn₃O₄ and Co₂O₃ is 5.0. A decrease in the pH of the solution assists the formation of a lower oxide presumably due to the relatively low concentration of OH⁻ ions discharged at the anode from acid solutions. On increasing the pH of the solution above 6, with Mn₂O₃ and Mn₃O₄ oxides, the percentage of the lower oxide also increases. This might be due to the increased reducing action of formaldehyde which becomes pronounced in alkaline medium. With Co₂O₃ increase in the pH from 5 to 7 exerts no effect on the oxide composition. On increasing the pH of the

solution, with CoO and MnO oxides, a higher oxide is deposited. The effect of alkalinity on the deposition of Co_3O_4 indicated that a higher oxide is deposited on increasing the alkalinity from 14.7-18.0N. A lower oxide is produced at relatively low alkalinities.

Effect of Some Added Salts

The effect of potassium chloride on the deposition of Co_3O_4 indicates that chloride ions assist the oxidation of the lower cobalt species which might be formed due to the reaction of the CoO_2^- with formaldehyde. Thus the decrease in the concentration of potassium chloride causes the formation of a lower oxide. The effect of sodium fluoride, sodium carbonate and pyrogallol on the deposition of Co_3O_3 , CoO and MnO oxides indicates that these salts assist the formation of a coherent deposit.

It is probable that the adsorption of these salts or their oxidation products as CO_2 or fluoride ions on the anodic oxide films protects them from oxidation. Sodium fluoride and sodium carbonate also assist the buffering of the solution.

The Effect of Ammonium Salts

Ammonium salts prevent the precipitation of manganese ions or other manganese salts as the pH is raised by the addition of ammonium hydroxide. Also they improve the buffering capacity and stability of the manganese complex present and increase the conductivity of the electrolyte.

The Effect of Current Density

Increase of current density leads to the formation of an oxide with a high percentage of MnO_2 or Co_2O_3 . This is quite distinct in the case of MnO, CoO and Co_3O_4 oxides. Decrease in the current density with Mn_2O_3 , Mn_3O_4 and Co_3O_4 oxides promotes the formation of a lower oxide, due to the small rate of the anodic reactions involving formation of higher oxides compared to reducing action of the reducing agents present towards these higher oxides.

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